

2022, vol. 9, issue 1, 225-233

RESEARCH ARTICLE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6795791>

The Role of Edupreneurs in Islamic Boarding Schools: A Case Study in Al-Ustmani

Hendri Hermawan ADINUGRAHA, IAIN Pekalongan, Indonesia

Shovil MUNA, IAIN Pekalongan, Indonesia

MUSTHOFA, UIN Walisongo, Indonesia

Abstract

This study intends to describe the role of Edupreneur in Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School. The method used in this study uses a qualitative approach. In this study, researchers used exploratory and descriptive research forms. The setting of this research is the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling technique, namely the technique of determining sampling with certain considerations, based on considerations that the samples in this study were students, teachers, and the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School foundation. The technique used for data collection and validity is source triangulation. The findings of this study state that edupreneurs at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School play an important role in the progress of the current world of education. Entrepreneurship or edupreneur education, such as that carried out by the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School Foundation, is naturally required for all Islamic religious education institutions, so it is no longer only recommended as it is today. In the Edupreneurship of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School, the students must be invited to the field to see business objects directly. Before graduating, the students of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School must be required to practice entrepreneurship with capital from the institution, which capital must be returned after the students graduate from the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School without interest. Entrepreneurship learning at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School is not all theoretical, but there is practice in laboratories and workshops to produce products, so that students and graduates have experience in producing products that can open up business opportunities. The Edupreneurship curriculum at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School is designed to produce graduates who are able to think creatively in order to produce innovators who are able to create change and progress for the Indonesian nation.

Keywords: Education; entrepreneurship; and edupreneur

1 Introduction

Global competition is already very fierce and cannot be avoided, so that it becomes a challenge for the Indonesian state. Almost every country competes to highlight the advantages of their respective resources. Empowerment of economic resources can be done if the human resources in the country have the competence, skills, expertise, and sufficient knowledge to develop these resources. However, it is certain that they will be unable to compete globally, if there is a lack of human resource knowledge, lack of HR skills, limited job opportunities and lack of attention from the government to create jobs (Sulistiandi & Rahayu, 2017).

Unemployment and poverty are still the scourge of the Indonesian nation and even become a big task for the Indonesian government, because these conditions will gradually disrupt Indonesia's economic stability (Wiranatakusuma & Primambudi, 2021). Therefore, increasing entrepreneurial knowledge becomes a necessity. These efforts can be made by developing an entrepreneurship curriculum from school to university, so that the younger generation or millennial generation has skills and competencies in terms of entrepreneurship (Horng et al., 2021). This is a solution to the problems above (Rueff, 2020), because Indonesia will find it difficult to become a strong country that has economic stability without being driven by the addition of new start-ups who start businesses which will eventually lead to new job vacancies for the Indonesian people.

It is very important to know that the condition of the people of the State of Indonesia to this day is abundant with a wealth of natural resources, therefore, as a society with education, do not only look for work but also must be able to create jobs by means of entrepreneurship.

On the other hand, the problem that arises is the number of unemployment rates in Indonesia is always increasing every year. The highest unemployment rate is for university graduates in Indonesia. The increase in the unemployment rate is always associated with schools or educational institutions, as institutions that produce these prospective workers. The managers of higher education are in the spotlight of all parties, be it education observers, politicians, and even the government itself because they are considered unable to produce quality graduates. This unemployment occurs because the available job opportunities are not able to accommodate the existing workforce, or in other words the rate of increase in labor is not proportional to job growth (Nawir & Christiani, 2019).

According to data from BPS, one in 10 of the workforce is currently unemployed. Whereas according to research, every 1 percent economic growth is only able to create around 265,000 new jobs. With Indonesia's economic growth ranging from 6 percent, there are only around 1,590,000 new jobs available. Entrepreneurship is one solution to overcome unemployment (Al Ayyubi et al., 2018).

Entrepreneurship is considered the answer to overcome economic problems, especially to encourage economic growth and technological development (Soomro et al., 2019). In order for economic growth to be achieved in accordance with the target, a planned and structured effort is needed. One of the efforts that can be made to encourage the creation of more entrepreneurs is to provide entrepreneurship education. In addition to having an impact on increasing economic growth, entrepreneurial activities are also related to creating jobs (Hani, 2019). Several developing countries in the Southeast Asian region, Malaysia, Sri Lanka and Indonesia believe that to reduce the number of significant increases in unemployment over the last five years, entrepreneurship is considered a solution to the growing unemployment problem, especially in these countries (Shamsudin et al., 2017). So it can be said that entrepreneurship is a solution to a country's economic problems. Because entrepreneurship is a solution, there needs to be a way to create new entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurship education includes development in various fields such as knowledge, capacity, behavior and individual qualities in cultivating entrepreneurial attitudes (Ratten & Usmanij, 2021). So it can be concluded that the focus of entrepreneurship education is on the process of creating a particular business which will eventually lead to and foster interest in entrepreneurship.

In recent years, research on entrepreneurship has increased both in terms of quantity and quality (Ndou et al., 2019; Mei et al., 2020; Blankesteyn et al., 2021; Deveci, 2022). This arises because entrepreneurial interest affects economic growth, technological development, dynamics of innovative processes and job creation (Asghar et al., 2019).

Entrepreneurship education can be started from Islamic boarding schools (Hasan et al., 2020), including the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School. The current curriculum applied at Al-Ustmani tends to be theoretical, this also contributes to the unpreparedness of graduates to choose self-employment or entrepreneurship careers because students are only prepared to continue or enter college. Likewise, college graduates are generally prepared to work as employees. Choosing an entrepreneurial career is an extraordinary case (Sar, 2017). Based on the problems or events above, there are several ways that the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School can do to minimize or suppress the number of unemployed in Indonesia, one of which is to provide entrepreneurial education to

students from an early age, so that by giving views or directions on entrepreneurship, students are expected to have the necessary knowledge and skills and high spirit of entrepreneurial concept. Observing the various problems mentioned above, the researcher offers an entrepreneurial model based on religious education at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School.

Edupreneurship which has a combined meaning of education and entrepreneurship is a unity that cannot be separated from its meaning. The two become one unit because the process carried out is indeed a reflection of the concept of entrepreneurship education, which means educating someone to be able to do and produce something of selling value and then it can be used by himself or a group (Wardana et al., 2020).

As for the purpose of implementing edupreneurship, it is none other than in line with the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System in Chapter II Article 3 concerning Basics, Functions, and Objectives which states that: National Education functions to develop capabilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation. In order to educate the nation's life, it aims to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe, fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens (Government, 2003).

Edupreneurship needs to be developed at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School, because its existence is in line with the law, namely developing self-potential so that it can create independence. Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state. Self-potential that continues to be honed and developed can make students have quality Human Resources (HR) who are competitive at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School. Qualified students at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School are assets that support a person to develop themselves and live in society in Indonesia.

2 Introduction to Edupreneur

Edupreneurship is a combination of two words in English, namely education and entrepreneurship. These two words are put together with the intention of creating a new meaning. As for literally, in the English – Indonesian Dictionary by John M. Echols and Hassan Shadily, the meaning of education is education. While entrepreneurship literally has the meaning of entrepreneurship (Williams, 1961).

Edupreneurship is an approach through learning scenarios that can bring student entrepreneurial ideas to life (Kuat & Santosa, 2020). Edupreneurship-oriented learning approach is entrepreneurship education which in the learning process that focuses on entrepreneurship activities both in theory and practice is an innovative learning approach that emphasizes teaching and learning activities that are linked to real objects or contextual, so that in addition to educating, this approach allows students to study the process of processing a material into a product that is useful and has economic value.

An edupreneur or educational entrepreneur is someone who has obtained his formal knowledge at an educational institution, then devotes all his knowledge and skills to the reality of business in order to create professional entrepreneurs (Darwish, 2019). In order for the role of an edupreneur to be effective, a model called the edupreneurial cycle is needed, so that the energy, enthusiasm, and creativity of the edupreneur towards their playing fields are maintained. The edupreneurial cycle will ensure accountability from the leadership of educational institutions, teachers and the community so as to produce a business plan that will answer the key questions: “what, why, who, how, and when” which will translate business ideas into blueprints.

Edupreneurship is a unique part of entrepreneurship in the field of education. Entrepreneurship is a creative or innovative business by seeing or creating opportunities and realizing them into something that has added value (economic, social, etc.). Entrepreneurship in the social field is called sociopreneurship, in the field of education it is called edupreneurship, internally it is called entrepreneurship, in the field of technology business it is called teknopreneurship (Halil, 2021).

Meanwhile, the edupreneurship as schools/educational institutions that always carry out meaningful innovations in a systemically, transformational change, without regard to existing resources, current capacities or national pressures in order to create new educational opportunities and excellence (Phillips & Filmer-Sankey, 2020). These two meanings have different meanings. In the first sense, edupreneurship is more profit-oriented which gives a lot of financial benefits. The second definition is more general, namely all creative and innovative efforts of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School which are oriented towards excellence.

3 Transformation of the Entrepreneurial Mindset of Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School Students

The development of entrepreneurship at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School has started from the formulation of the curriculum. The design of the integration of entrepreneurship in the curriculum was agreed upon in the work shop of the Al-Ustmani curriculum with reference to entrepreneurship based on Islamic boarding school values and akhlakul karimah. Al-Ustmani has developed his students to have science and technology insight and entrepreneurship. Al-Ustmani always increases the participation of students through community service and collaborates with various parties in the field of entrepreneurship education.

Entrepreneurship in the mission of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School wants to show its distinction with other Islamic boarding schools. Entrepreneurship in this case is positioned as another competency possessed by Al-Ustmani after the main competencies and supporting competencies. Based on the mission, it is then described in the objectives of organizing the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School, such as producing professional and competent students; produce productive Islamic basic education researchers; produce reliable human devout devout; produce students who have an entrepreneurial mentality, are reliable, and competent.

Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School has emphasized the importance of the entrepreneurial spirit so that it can become a character that is attached to its students. These entrepreneurial values include the value of entrepreneurial character which is expected to be internalized in the mindset, attitude and action patterns of the graduates of Islamic boarding schools. These values include: Independent, creative, innovative, confident, task and action oriented, risk-taking, leadership, forward-looking, hard working, honest, disciplined, curious, and motivated to move forward.

Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School graduates have these characteristics and entrepreneurial spirit as the basic foundation in stepping into an entrepreneur because in principle the transformation of values as well as the entrepreneurial mindset is the basic process in starting entrepreneurship. Because to become a successful entrepreneur, it takes several steps to transform mindsets and paradigms in order to run a business.

The stages of the process of transforming the character and entrepreneurial mindset of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School students are as follows: transformation of mindset; transformation of old ways of thinking to change. Changed from a habit of always using logic to a creative mindset in finding inspiration, ideas and business opportunities (Clark, 2004). Ways of thinking that need to be transformed are avoiding logical traps, thinking differently from others, using knowledge and education as a medium for finding inspiration through creative and innovative thinking patterns and visionary thinking; entrepreneurial transformation from being an entrepreneur; entrepreneurial transformation from an owner mindset to an investor mindset. After the businessman is successful, his mindset develops, wanting to become an investor to develop his business through business expansion, buying business, franchising businesses and increasing company values so that it leads to an increase in real asset values that are high in tangible and intangible terms so that a company not valued from real assets but has turned into a priceless asset for the students of Al-Ustmani.

Edupreneurship is one of the graduate profiles to anticipate graduates who are not all able to be absorbed into the world of work (Nurjaya et al., 2020). There is a possibility, not all of the graduates of Al-Ustmani can all continue on to higher education. Al-Ustmani has prepared a number of skills to become entrepreneurs so that graduates can survive in their lives and can face the future.

Entrepreneurial qualifications and entrepreneurial competencies can be provided through a series of programs and learning experiences at Al-Ustmani both from theoretical knowledge and entrepreneurship experience facilitated by Al-Ustmani as well as the ability to cooperate with strategic sectors such as the industrial world through apprenticeship processes and others. This is done in the context of the transfer of knowledge, skills and experience to Al-Ustmani students through theoretical learning and entrepreneurial practice to internalize the entrepreneurial spirit and mindset on an ongoing basis and have a planned, systematic and sustainable management system.

Many problems arise in the education of Islamic boarding schools, including many graduates of Islamic boarding schools who are unable to be absorbed in the world of work. Unemployment, especially graduates of Islamic boarding schools, is a problem that is reasonable enough to immediately find an alternative solution. Another problem faced by Islamic boarding schools is the low competence of their graduates so that the output of higher education does not yet have the competencies that are expected and needed by the community and have low competitiveness in the world of work. Thus, most of the graduates of Islamic boarding schools tend to be more job seekers (Ulya, 2017). The results of Pelipa & Marganingsih's research (2019) stated that edupreneurship partially has a significant influence on increasing student abilities.

The urgency of entrepreneurship education at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School is to shape the entrepreneurial character of students; open the entrepreneurial mindset of students; demands for the development of entrepreneurship curriculum in Islamic boarding schools; and following the trend of Islamic boarding schools which are currently based on entrepreneurship.

4 Edupreneur Learning Strategies at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School

The demographic bonus will last until 2030 with a dependency ratio of 0.4–0.5. Through this demographic bonus, Indonesia has a great opportunity to increase productivity and economic growth in order to support the nation's welfare. However, the demographic bonus also has negative impacts that arise if it is not used properly, namely it can increase the number of unemployment and social inequality and result in a drastic increase in penetration of social security and pensioners which will have an impact on stagnation in the national economy. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare for the younger generation to be able to take advantage of the demographic bonus properly (Adriani & Yustini, 2021).

One of the most appropriate steps to take advantage of the demographic bonus is to increase the number of entrepreneurs because by increasing the number of entrepreneurs it can increase the number of jobs, reduce the dependency ratio, reduce the number of poverty in the aggregate and increase state revenue through taxes. In this regard, that education is the right means to be able to take advantage of the demographic bonus to increase the number of entrepreneur in the future through early Islamic education. Instilling values from an early age will result in faster and more complete internalization (Joan & S., T. W. Setyoko, 2020).

Entrepreneurship learning activities at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School which require interesting media in the form of student cooperatives, santri gardens are opportunities for the growth of entrepreneurial souls in students. The high need for an entrepreneurial spirit at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School has resulted in the creation of edupreneur ideas which have indirectly emerged, teachers take advantage of the work of learning activities to be marketed in media expos or the santri market. Expo activities or santri markets are usually in the form of exhibitions of students' artworks, which can be in the form of paintings, origami, mosaics, or other artistic creations (Lestari et al., n.d.). These artworks can then be sold or auctioned, then the proceeds from the sale or auction proceeds are donated to victims of natural disasters, to finance an activity, or to cash for the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School.

The first step in developing edupreneurship is to prepare teachers who are able to guide students so that they have an entrepreneurial spirit. If the teacher resources are ready, the quality improvement policy and edupreneurship culture will be supported. Edupreneurship requires support from

educators who have a teacherpreneur spirit. Educators who have a teacherpreneur spirit are educators who have leadership traits, master many innovative teaching strategies, have ideas and strategies so that institutions can achieve high success, have the skills and commitment to disseminate their expertise to others (Maydiantoro et al., 2021).

Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School teachers who have innovative teaching strategies will provide positive energy to their students, to be more active and innovative in developing the ideas and knowledge they get. The role of the teacherpreneur is highly dependent on the support of educational institutions and community organizations. Some educational institutions use educators who have the potential to become teacherpreneurs as curriculum material developers, mentors, strategic planners, produce patterns of collaboration with other institutions, and so on. A good educational institution needs to see the potential of its educators. Educators who have the potential to become teacherpreneurs need support from institutions. Likewise, educational institutions where educators take shelter, should also provide opportunities for teachers to channel their potential as teacherpreneurs to develop ideas that are useful for the progress of the institution, and also as a vehicle to channel their entrepreneurial potential. The second step is to design creative and interesting learning activities using creative strategies, the third step is to prepare the tools and media that will be used in the activity, the fourth step is to apply learning activities. The fifth step is to market learning products at Al Islamic Boarding Schools.

Edupreneurship can be introduced to students at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School. Having a trained entrepreneurial mentality can optimize aspects of student development. The students' extraordinary brain development makes them a tireless learner. Edupreneurship values can be introduced to students through religious learning at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School which is one of the lessons that uses quite a lot of media and teaching aids. How to implement edupreneur in the learning process using creative learning strategies. The use of creative learning strategies is considered effective for packaging edupreneurs in religious learning at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School.

Edupreneurship can be interpreted as entrepreneurship education at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School. Edupreneurship can be given to anyone without age restrictions. Everyone has the right to become an entrepreneur or entrepreneur, including educators and even students at Islamic boarding schools. Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School educators can take advantage of opportunities to make media such as books, modules, and others, so that they can organize fun learning for students. Edupreneur education will be implemented effectively if it is packaged in creative learning strategies carried out by teachers in teaching and learning activities, especially religious learning at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School. Thus, edupreneurship is expected to be able to give birth to young and talented entrepreneurs from among students at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School.

5 Implementation of the Edupreneurs Program at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School

Entrepreneurship education has been developed in almost all Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia with a very varied process that aims to create entrepreneurship, of course with various methods and strategies that make students interested in entrepreneurship (Kolade et al., 2022). Islamic Boarding Schools as one of the leading mediators and facilitators in building the nation's young generation have an obligation to teach, educate, train and motivate their students so that they become a smart generation that is independent, creative, innovative and able to create various job opportunities or business. Islamic boarding schools can become the backbone of the country's long-term economic improvement that is more futuristic if the competence of its graduates is directed according to the needs of the workforce and business development. This shows that Islamic Boarding Schools really understand the importance of entrepreneurship as a smart solution for their students to become young entrepreneurs who continue with the hope that each Islamic Boarding School is serious in making material designs and presenting learning methods, including the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School.

To give birth to these successful young entrepreneurs, it requires sincerity and seriousness from the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School in carrying out the entrepreneurial mission of the Islamic Boarding School. Entrepreneurship programs that have been initiated and run by various Islamic boarding schools, especially in Al-Ustmani, should be used as examples in focusing Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding Schools in producing young entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs.

Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School has an understanding that entrepreneurship education is not only business business education, so it can be studied by all students in various fields of science. The concept of entrepreneurship education that is able to produce entrepreneurs is education that not only relies on concepts and theories, but is also combined with real practice or business. Entrepreneurship education at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School can be designed to know, to do, and to be entrepreneurs. On the other hand, entrepreneurship education is education and training that allows students to develop and use their creativity, take initiative, responsibility and risk. Thus entrepreneurship education does not only focus on business or enterprise education (Dima & Meghisan-Toma, 2018). The outputs of entrepreneurship education at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School can be entrepreneurs or business entrepreneurs and intrapreneurs as academic entrepreneurs, corporate entrepreneurs and social entrepreneurs. The value of entrepreneurship applied to educational institutions gave rise to a new term, namely edupreneurship. Edupreneurship is a school that always carries out systemic meaningful innovation, transformational change, regardless of existing resources, current capacities or national pressures in order to create new educational opportunities and excellence (Nautika et al., 2019). With this understanding, edupreneurship is one way to solve the problem of not forming an entrepreneurial spirit in Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School. From the triangulation results at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School, it is obtained that the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School is worthy of being the object of study in this research because it has implemented edupreneurship on its students.

Entrepreneurship education at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School does not only teach entrepreneurship theory, but more on practical applications that encourage the emergence of an entrepreneur mindset among teachers and students. The implementation of entrepreneurship education at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School needs to be studied more deeply, especially those related to the aims and objectives of entrepreneurship education. There is a growing thought that there are various entrepreneurship education targets, ranging from aspects of entrepreneurial attitude, aspects of creating new jobs and even aspects of contributing to the community in helping local entrepreneurs to grow and develop. There is an understanding that develops in the minds of researchers that the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School should play a role in advancing the Indonesian nation; who are able to provide solutions and produce the impact of entrepreneurship education learning in the form of creating a generation of educated entrepreneurs.

The students of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School are expected to be creative and innovative people. Efforts to make students and graduates of Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School creative and innovative through Edupreneur can be done by cultivating creativity and innovation at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School, making nature a place of learning, establishing communication between teachers and students, solving problems, conducting curriculum and learning creative ones. Entrepreneurship learning (Edupreneurship) can shape the mentality of students to be creative and innovative, and can prevent graduates from becoming unemployed. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a national curriculum for entrepreneurship for students in Islamic boarding schools.

The students of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School must continue to be motivated to be creative and innovative because with this nature they are able to create new products that are expected by the business world, as well as a sign that our country is achieving growth and progress. With this creative and innovative nature, students or graduates of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School can produce new products that are able to open up business opportunities.

6 Conclusion

Edupreneurs at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School play an important role in the progress of the current world of education. Entrepreneurship or Edupreneur education, such as that conducted by the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School Foundation, is naturally required for all Islamic religious education institutions, so it is no longer only recommended as it is today. In the Edupreneurship of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School, the students must be invited to the field to see business objects directly. Before graduating, the students of the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School must be required to practice entrepreneurship with capital from the institution, which capital must be returned after the students graduate from the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School without interest. Entrepreneurship learning at the Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School is not all theoretical, but there is practice in laboratories and workshops to produce products, so that students and graduates have experience in producing products that can open up business opportunities. The Edupreneurship curriculum at Al-Ustmani Islamic Boarding School is designed to produce graduates who are able to think creatively in order to produce innovators who are able to create change and progress for the Indonesian nation.

References

- Adriani, D., & Yustini, T. (2021). Anticipating The Demographic Bonus From The Perspective Of Human Capital In Indonesia. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147- 4478), 10(6). <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i6.1377>
- Al Ayyubi, W. U., Setyanti, S. W. L. H., & Suroso, I. (2018). The role of self efficacy as mediating the influence of family environment and social environment on student entrepreneur interest. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 7(7).
- Asghar, M. Z., Gul, F., Hakkarainen, P. S., & Zeki Taşdemir, M. (2019). Validating Entrepreneurial Intentions Questionnaire To Assess The Impact Of Entrepreneurship Education. *Egitim ve Bilim*, 44(197). <https://doi.org/10.15390/EB.2019.6105>
- Blankesteyn, M., Bossink, B., & van der Sijde, P. (2021). Science-Based Entrepreneurship Education As A Means For University-Industry Technology Transfer. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 17(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-019-00623-3>
- Clark, B. R. (2004). Delineating the character of the entrepreneurial university. *Higher Education Policy*, 17(4). <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.hep.8300062>
- Darwish, H. (2019). Open Educational Resources (OER) Edupreneurship Business Models For Different Stakeholders. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24(6). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-09962-8>
- Deveci, İ. (2022). Review of Entrepreneurship Education Literature In Educational Contexts: Bibliometric Analysis. In *Participatory Educational Research* (Vol. 9, Issue 1). <https://doi.org/10.17275/per.22.12.9.1>
- Dima, A.-M., & Meghisan-Toma, G.-M. (2018). Reserch on Implementing Education For Sustainable Development. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.2478/picbe-2018-0027>
- Government, R. of I. (2003). Law Of The Republic Of Indonesia Number 20 Year 2003 Concerning National Education Systems. In *President of the Republic Indonesia*.
- Halil, H. (2021). Pengembangan Edupreneurship Di Pesantren. *Journal of Education*, 1(2).
- Hani, U. (2019). Government Partnership Social Entrepreneurs In Poverty Alleviation. *Journal of Economic Empowerment Strategy (JEES)*, 02(02).
- Hasan, M., Hatidja, S., Abd. Rasyid, R., Nurjanna, Walenta, A. S., Tahir, J., & Ikhwan Maulana Haeruddin, M. (2020). Entrepreneurship education, intention, and self efficacy: An examination of knowledge transfer within family businesses. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 8(1). [https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.8.1\(37\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.8.1(37))
- Horng, J. S., Hsiao, H. L., Liu, C. H., Chou, S. F., & Chung, Y. C. (2021). Learning innovative entrepreneurship: Developing an influential curriculum for undergraduate hospitality students. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport and Tourism Education*, 29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2020.100289>
- Joan, K., & S., T. W. Setyoko, H. (2020). Puzzel Wira : Sarana Edupreneurship Berbasis Mobile Multimedia Untuk Generasi Alpha di Era Disrupsi Teknologi. *Indonesian Journal of Social Science Education (IJSSE)*, 2.
- Kolade, O., Osabuohien, E., Aremu, A., Olanipekun, K. A., Osabohien, R., & Tunji-Olayeni, P. (2022). Co-creation of Entrepreneurship Education: Challenges and Opportunities for University, Industry and Public

Sector Collaboration in Nigeria. In *The Palgrave Handbook of African Entrepreneurship*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75894-3_11

Kuat, T., & Santosa, B. (2020). Edupreneurship through teaching factory in vocational school of hospitality expertise. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(4).

Lestari, E. A., Cahyani, L. G., & Purworejo, U. M. (n.d.). Strategi pembelajaran kreatif berbasis edupreneur dalam pengembangan pembelajaran ipa. 168-179.

Maydiantoro, A., Ridwan, R., Tusianah, R., Rachman, A., Kesuma, P., Isnainy, U. C. A. S., & Zainaro, M. A. (2021). Entrepreneurship in Higher Education Curricula: Evidence from Indonesia. *Psychology And Education*, 58(3).

Mei, H., Lee, C. H., & Xiang, Y. (2020). Entrepreneurship Education And Students' Entrepreneurial Intention In Higher Education. *Education Sciences*, 10(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10090257>

Nautika, J., I, J. P. L., & Dhuwur, B. (2019). Studi Analisa Pembentukan Edupreneurship Maritim Di Politeknik Maritim Negeri Indonesia. 7(1), 38-47.

Nawir, C. P., & Christiani, N. (2019). The Effect of Entrepreneurial Passion and Opportunity Awareness toward the Sustainability of Startup Businesses. *Jurnal Entrepreneur Dan Entrepreneurship*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.37715/jee.v8i1.1115>

Ndou, V., Mele, G., & Del Vecchio, P. (2019). Entrepreneurship Education In Tourism: An Investigation Among European Universities. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport and Tourism Education*, 25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2018.10.003>

Nurjaya, N., Sobarna, A., Affandi, A., Erlangga, H., & Sarwani, S. (2020). Edupreneurship management in shaping the nation ' s character. 8(3), 198-206.

Pelipa, E. D., & Marganingsih, A. (2019). Pengaruh Edupreneurship Dan Praktek Kerja Terhadap Kemampuan Life Skill Mahasiswa. *JURKAMI: Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.31932/jpe.v4i1.422>

Phillips, D., & Filmer-Sankey, C. (2020). The Oxford project. In *Diversificatn Mod Lang Teachng*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203975909-12>

Ratten, V., & Usmanij, P. (2021). Entrepreneurship education: Time for a change in research direction? *International Journal of Management Education*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2020.100367>

Rueff, S. (2020). Creative Freedom: Arts Entrepreneurship as a Mindset. *Journal of Arts Entrepreneurship Education*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.46776/jaee.v2.57>

Sar, A. K. (2017). The Influence Of Management Education On Entrepreneurship Success. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 20(2).

Shamsudin, S. F. F. B., Al Mamun, A., Nawir, N. B. C., Nasir, N. A. B. M., & Zakaria, M. N. Bin. (2017). Factors Affecting Entrepreneurial Intention Among the Malaysian University Students. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 51(4).

Soomro, M. A., Memon, M. S., & Bukhari, N. S. (2019). Entrepreneurial Education And Its Impact On Entrepreneurial Intentions: A Comparative Analysis Of Business Graduates Of Public And Private Universities Of Sindh. *Pacific Business Review International*, 12(6).

Ulya, I. (2017). Implementasi Pengembangan Enterpreneurship Dalam Kurikulum Prodi Pgmi Institut Pesantren Mathali'ul Falah Pati-Jawa Tengah. *QUALITY*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.21043/quality.v5i2.3060>

Wahyu Sulistiandi & Rahayu, S. (2017). Assessment Of First Sharia Hospital Certification In Indonesia Facing The Global Competition. *Batusangkar International Conference* 11.

Wardana, L. W., Narmaditya, B. S., Wibowo, A., Mahendra, A. M., Wibowo, N. A., Harwida, G., & Rohman, A. N. (2020). The Impact Of Entrepreneurship Education And Students' Entrepreneurial Mindset: The Mediating Role Of Attitude And Self-Efficacy. *Heliyon*, 6(9). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04922>

Williams, G. E. (1961). : *An Indonesian-English Dictionary* . John M. Echols, Hassan Shadily. *American Anthropologist*, 63(6). <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1961.63.6.02a00420>

Wiranatakusuma, D. B., & Primambudi, G. (2021). Determinants of Poverty in Indonesia. *Sociologia y Tecnociencia*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.24197/st.2.2021.243-267>